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2. Effectiveness of Interactive Smart Board (ISB), in Teaching of Science Subject - A Literature Review

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Abstract :

The aim of teaching science is to develop an intuitive understanding of abstract concepts, but in traditional classroom abstract concepts are difficult to explain to the students thus they have to understand science by memorizing and mechanical learning. The Interactive Smart Board (ISB) is an excellent way of learning and understanding concepts in science, and easy for the teachers to make students understand science concepts by making abstract learning into realistic and concrete. There are different collaborative and communication tools in the ISB which makes teaching and learning interactive and interesting (Mata, Lazar, Nedeff, & Lazar, 2013). The aim of this is to present the content in which teachers can make abstract science concept into concrete by using ISB tools, web 2.0 technology and plugins, these tools can also be used for communicating, collaborating, interacting and stimulating student's creative potential. In this paper a literature review was conducted for analysis of Effectiveness of Interactive Smart Board (ISB), in teaching of abstract concepts in science subject and also making teaching interactive. After review and analysis from different sources such as, Scopus, DOAJ, Google Scholar, Academia, Science Direct, it was concluded that ISB and its interactive tools are effective in making abstract concepts simple, concrete and interactive thus making learning & teaching effective and efficient. It was also concluded the effectiveness of ISB tools in collaborating and communicating information effectively.

In a traditional classroom Blackboard and Chalk are the tools in the hands of teacher for making teaching effective and efficient, these tools help teachers in making abstract and complex concepts in science into concrete and simpler, but they are not much attractive, do not store information, animation and integration of audio and video are not possible. These drawbacks were removed with the advent of Information and communication technology, in a classroom the robust Interactive Smart Board (ISB), has replaced traditional blackboard and made teaching and learning more effective. Thus helped teacher in making intuitive understanding of abstract, complex, indefinite and actual representation of concept. ISB and its tools make learning interactive, learner centered and interesting by making learners to participate in teaching &

learning, construct knowledge, collaborate with team and communicate with teacher. As cited in (Baig, 2017) An eLearning platform is widely used in the smart classrooms, as it provides fastest, cost-effective and consistent communication between the teachers and learners. In the traditional classroom teaching information is delivered through the use of tools such as whiteboard, chalk, duster, flannel board, presentation software and power points, but these tools are static and are not much effective in teaching and communicating with these tools also does not enhance learning among the learners. But modern E-learning sites, smart classes and Learning Management System (LMS) are dynamic and have high quality content and instructional design that makes learning and communication most effective. Effectiveness of ISB are evident from the findings of (Stoica, Paragina, Paragina, Miron, & Jipa, 2011), it was observe in their findings that, ISB has many advantages for teachers who use it as a teaching instrument. In their study they have observed that the advantages include the ability to manipulate objects in real time, efficiency in presenting a lesson and support for the long-term planning and use of resources. Students can benefit from these files with everything that has been previously visualized enriched with web documents. In this study the researcher has concluded that the classes where the interactive whiteboard was used were very interesting for the students, thus arousing interest among students and also motivate them, thus the interactive whiteboard contributes to the growth of interaction between students while performing a task. In this study scope is limited to the study of only abstract and interactive teaching of science concepts only, but it has wide scope in different subjects where ISB can be used, for example in Mathematics and Geometry abstract concepts can be explained with concrete examples and visualizations for intuitive understanding of the concepts to the learner.

Keywords: MOODLE, Learning Management System (LMS), ELearning, Online Learning, Interactive White Board (IWB).

Objectives of the Study

In this study the problem investigated is about analyzing, the effectiveness of Interactive Smart Board (ISB), in teaching of abstract concepts in science subject through literature review and collaboration and communication of information.

The objectives of research are as follows:

- Review the effectiveness of Interactive Smart Board (ISB) tools in explaining the abstract concept by teachers.
- Review the effectiveness of Interactive Smart Board (ISB) tools in Intuitive understanding of abstract concept by students.

- Study the use of Interactive Smart Board (ISB) tools by teachers and learners in collaborating learning, through literature review.
- Study the use of Interactive Smart Board (ISB) tools by teachers and learners in communication of information, through literature review.

Methods adopted

In this study, analysis of literature is conducted by using data base of Scopus, Science direct, Google Scholar, Online Journals, Academia, Google Search Engines, Open educational resources and Websites. The Scopus, Science Direct, Open Educational Research source, Directory of Open Access Journals (DOAJ) is searched for finding Abstracts and Journals to study applications of Interactive Smart Board tools for making teaching effective and efficient by explaining abstract concepts into concrete and intuitive understanding of science. By using the following combinations of key words “Interactive Smart Board tools and Use/Applications”, “Interactive Smart Board tools and Communications” “Effectiveness and Interactive Smart Board tools”, “Educational use of Interactive Smart Board tools”, “Interactive Smart Board tools and Effective Teaching Learning”, “Interactive Smart Board tools and Collaboration”, and “Interactive Smart Board tools and Learning”, “Interactive Smart Board tools and Abstract / Concrete learning”, a data base is analyzed to study the effectiveness “Interactive Smart Board tools and Learning” and “Interactive Smart Board tools and Ineffectiveness”. In these search more than 60 studies have been identified, which uses “Interactive Smart Board tools in teaching & learning and communication of information. Beside Journals other useful database such as Reference Books, Reference Sources, and Reports, Websites and Handbooks on Research, are also reviewed for the study of tools.

Literature Review and Analysis of Literature

In their study (Mata et al., 2013), has observed that benefits and facilities of interactive smart boards in teaching Science and Technology subjects, the impact of eco-technology upon education is highlighted in the first part of paper together with an eco-teaching impact measurement model, following the analysis of latest approaches focused on integration of innovative environmentally friendly materials and technological solutions in the educational context. The solution generated by exploiting the resources of eco-technology in education is represented by interactive smart boards. According to (Beeland, 2002), the use of interactive whiteboards in the classroom does lead to increased student engagement, the researcher observe that the primary reason of engagement appears to be the visual aspects of using the whiteboard. Thus, school and technology leaders need to be aware of the potential these whiteboards have for increasing student achievement through increased student engagement. Effectively using this

information, in conjunction with other school improvement efforts, has the potential to greatly assist educators in their efforts to attract and maintain student attention and to improve student achievement. In their study (Maněnová&Žembová, 2012), observed that the interactive smart board fulfilled several intellectual functions: it made pupils think as well as develop their powers of imagination and attention; and it had an epistemological function, as it made it possible to connect a concrete reality with its abstract expression. Further they observed that the most powerful effect of using the interactive whiteboard is the way it increases motivation. Web 2.0 tools, such as Wiziq can be integrated into ISB, for interactivity, engagement, collaboration and communication, this tool was studied by (Baig, 2011), in research "Effectiveness of Social Networking sites in communication of information in distance Education". According to (Baig, 2011), 'Wiziq.com' provides online tools for communication of information and therefore it is used for the study of effectiveness of online learning on students' achievement. In this study researcher found a high score in achievement among students' taught and studied through online tools and online learning environment which was used as a learning tool for communication and collaboration of information. Similarly, achievement among students of F2F (face to face) teaching was found low, this is because in F2F learning, collaborating and sharing of resources is limited to the walls of classroom, but online learning made possible to learning, collaborating, and sharing of resources beyond four walls. Online learning environment provides features such as, user center, user control and communication, and making teaching learning process learner centric. (Bidaki&Mobasheri, 2013) reported that ISB, positively increases pedagogical skills, further they observed that the number of existing investigations into the pedagogical skills required for good practice in using ICT. The findings from the research provides some evidence that these skills dramatically changed in a class practicing with the ISB. Further they reported that the process of changing skills and adaptation with new pedagogy methods for using this new technology is easy. According to (Türel&Demirli, 2010), the effects of ISBs on students' learning have been proved in the literature, but the main source of this achievement relies on the design process of ISB materials. The researcher selected eighty ISB-M designers in this study and they were investigated in terms of three dimensions: Software and tools, ISB features, and teaching methods and techniques. The results show that designers were employed a wide range of software and tools including graphic and animation, sound, picture, video processing software and web design software as well as utilities such as gif-to-swf converters in order to create visual, interactive and usable materials. They also considered and utilized a variety of ISB features including particularly mouse function, screen-shade, annotation, spotlight, gallery, and highlighting. Finally, designers benefited from various teaching methods and techniques either

alone or combined with the others while designing their ISB. Thus effectiveness of ISB increases with the use of animations, graphs images and figures. In their study (Maněnová&Žembová, 2012), observed that the interactive smart board develops students power of imagination, thinking, attention and make it possible to connect a concrete reality with its abstract expression.

As cited in (Bidaki&Mobasheri, 2013) there are research findings which are in contrast with findings of effectiveness of ISB and ICT, according to some study the teachers generally did not feel that use of the ISB had really changed their classroom practicing. As there is no exact border between different teaching practices, this discrepancy might be insignificant. Further it was observed in this study that the problems with the limited impact of ISB in teaching are more likely to happen if teachers cannot understand that interactivity requires a new approach to pedagogy. In their study (Tertemiz, Sahin, Can, &Duzgun, 2015), observed that both the teachers and students considered the ISB to be effective in terms of reducing distractions and improving student attention. However, both of them also indicate some technical problems and other negative aspects associated with the use of the internet. On the other hand, teachers emphasized the educational use of the whiteboard whereas students mostly focused on the whiteboard itself and on the classroom setting.

Findings

In this research an analysis of literature review has been done by using data base from Open Education Research, DOAJ, Google Scholars, Google Books, E-books, and Websites and it was found that ISB and its tools are very useful for the teachers in making their teaching more effective by engaging students with web 2.0 tools and ISB, further they also help teachers making their teaching more realistic with the web 2.0 tools and ISB tools. These tools make abstract and complex concepts more concrete and simple accurate representation of concepts and realistic drawings and animation of different concepts in science. Similarly, the learner's use tools in ISB and Web 2.0 tools in communication, sharing and collaboration of information, thus interactivity of the ISB makes abstract and difficult concepts concrete, easy and realistic, which help learners in developing intuitive understanding of abstract concepts. The findings and conclusion of effectiveness of ISB in teaching and learning in this study are also in agreement with the results in the literature review presented by various researchers. In one such study (Mata et al., 2013), has observed the benefits and facilities of interactive smart boards in teaching Science and Technology subjects. As reported by (Beeland, 2002), the use of interactive whiteboards in the classroom does lead to increased student engagement, the researcher observe that the primary reason of engagement appears to be the visual aspects of using the whiteboard. Thus ISB has the potential for increasing student achievement through increased student

engagement, participation and collaboration. The effectiveness of ISB was recorded in most of the findings but review of literature also suggests the ineffectiveness of ISB, in comparison with face to face and tools used in traditional classroom. As cited in (Bidaki&Mobasheri, 2013) there are research findings which are in contrast with findings of effectiveness of ISB and ICT, according to some study the teachers generally did not feel that use of the ISB had really changed their classroom practicing. As there is no exact border between different teaching practices, this discrepancy might be insignificant. Further it was observed in this study that the problems with the limited impact of ISB in teaching are more likely to happen if teachers cannot understand that interactivity requires a new approach to pedagogy. In their study (Tertemiz, Sahin, Can, &Duzgun, 2015), observed that both the teachers and students considered the ISB to be effective in terms of reducing distractions and improving student attention. However, both of them also indicate some technical problems and other negative aspects associated with the use of the internet. On the other hand, teachers emphasized the educational use of the whiteboard whereas students mostly focused on the whiteboard itself and on the classroom setting.

Conclusions

ISB is the most interactive, engaging and motivating technology, in the 21st Century, thus it enhances learning by making abstract concept into concrete and realistic. There web 2.0 tools embedded in the ISB which improves collaboration and communication among students and teachers. There are other tools also which engage learners and make their teaching more interactive, thus ISB make teaching learner centered. Therefore, ISB are effective in teaching and learning but there are few researches which suggests contrast findings, according to such research findings the teachers generally did not feel that use of the ISB had really changed their classroom practicing, they are not much effective in the classroom. Effectiveness of ISB is also limited in reducing distractions and improving attention and interactivity. According to (Tertemiz, Sahin, Can, &Duzgun, 2015), teachers emphasized the educational use of the whiteboard whereas students mostly focused on the whiteboard itself and on the classroom setting. Thus ISB are effective in empowering teachers to attract, concrete, engage learners and make teaching learning more interesting, interactive and student centered.

References

- Baig, M. A. (2011). RESEARCH PAPERS A CRITICAL STUDY OF EFFECTIVENESS OF ONLINE LEARNING ON STUDENTS ' ACHIEVEMENT. I-Manager's Journal of Educational Technology, 7(4), 28-34.

- Baig, M. A. (2017). A STUDY OF APPLICATION OF LEARNING MANAGEMENT SYSTEM (LMS) MOODLE. *An International Multidisciplinary Half Yearly Journal - ROYAL*, 42(1), 22–25. <https://doi.org/10.1104/pp.114.256404>
- Beeland, W. (2002). Student engagement, visual learning and technology: Can interactive whiteboards help? Annual Conference of the Association of Information Technology for Teaching Education. Retrieved from <http://citeseerx.ist.psu.edu/viewdoc/download?doi=10.1.1.135.3542&rep=rep1&type=pdf>
- Bidaki, M. Z., & Mobasheri, N. (2013). Teachers' Views of the Effects of the Interactive White Board (IWB) on Teaching. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 83, 140–144. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2013.06.027>
- Maněnová, M., & Žembová, N. (2012). Analysis of Lessons using Interactive Whiteboard focused on Pedagogical Interaction and Communication. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 69(Icepsy), 1719–1728. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2012.12.120>
- Mata, L., Lazar, I., Nedeff, V., & Lazar, G. (2013). Eno Interactive Whiteboards as an Innovative Eco-technology Solution in Teaching Science and Technological Subjects. *APCBEE Procedia*, 5, 312–316. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apcbee.2013.05.053>
- Stoica, D., Paragina, F., Paragina, S., Miron, C., & Jipa, A. (2011). The interactive whiteboard and the instructional design in teaching physics. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 15, 3316–3321. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2011.04.292>
- Tertemiz, N. (Istik), Sahin, D., Can, B., & Duzgun, S. (2015). Views of Primary School Teachers and Students about The Interactive Whiteboard. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 186, 1289–1297. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2015.04.099>
- Türel, Y. K., & Demirli, C. (2010). Instructional Interactive Whiteboard Materials: Designer's perspectives. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 9, 1437–1442. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2010.12.346>